

Women Self Help Groups (WSHGs): A Change Agent for Socio-economic Development in Soreng District, Sikkim, India

Dewan Rai¹, Prof. Sudhansu Sekher Mahapatra²

¹Research Scholars, Department of Commerce, School of Professional Studies, Sikkim University, Sikkim, India

²Professor & Dean, Department of Commerce, School of Professional Studies, Sikkim University, Sikkim, India

Corresponding author- **Dewan Rai**

Email: raidewan750@gmail.com

Abstract

Women Self Help Groups (WSHGs), now become one of the crucial instruments for microfinance in the area/locality so as to use for earning activities and solving common problems. In rural area, microfinance is also considered to be an instrumental tool for financing small scale business activities. The main purpose is to providing the financial support and services to poor people, upgrade of standard of living and empower to the rural women. WSHG can generates income and saving in the rural area. This paper focused into how WSHGs contribution towards the society and development of rural women in Sikkim. The development of rural women in terms of socio-economic development of their family, income, expenditure, saving etc. With the help of amenities provided by the government in order to increase their economic activities for development of society, state and nation also. It also examines the socio-economic status, the changes in the level of income, expenditure and saving before and after joining the WSHGs and the problems faced by the WSHGs' members. Primary data collected from Chakung village under Chumbong-Chakung block of Soreng District of West Sikkim. The sample size is considered for the study is 112 respondents from selected village. The descriptive and inferential statistics has been used for analyzing the data. In this study, frequency table's chart was also used. In order to testing the hypotheses, chi-square and descriptive statistics were used. The findings indicate that demographic and social-economic status of the respondents have indicated positive sign and favourable for the rural development in the study area. Therefore, there is change in economic conditions after joining the WSHGs. The average monthly household income and saving of respondents has increased after joining the WSHGs in the West Sikkim. The key role of WSHG is too self-reliant in the area/locality. So, that they can used their local resources and generating income for their development of society as well as nation also.

Keywords: Women Self Help Groups (WSHG), socio-economic status, Saving, Income, Z-test.

1. Introduction

Women Self Help Groups (WSHGs) is one of the important tools for poverty alleviation. WSHG have become more significance for people to work together, solving usual problem. It helps to improve socio-economic status in the village. WSHG is the dynamic platform to the people which self-reliant, self-sufficient, self-production, common responsibility by catalyze local available resource of the person in the group (Gaikwad & Reddy, 2013). In rural area, microfinance is also considered to be an instrumental tool for financing small scale business activities. There should be proper facilities for providing financial services required which is creative supply system and channels. Microfinance system is encouraged by the Government, Nationalized Bank, National Bank for Agricultural and Rural Development (NABARD), Cooperative Banks and various other institutions, so as to reduce the poverty level. The main objective is to providing the financial support and services to poor people, upgrade of standard of living and empower to the rural women (Gadkari, 2015).

As per NABARD, define WSHG is "small, economical homogeneous affinity groups of rural

poor, voluntarily formed to save and mutually contribute to a common fund to be lent to its members as per the group members' decision". In 1991-92, NABARD initiated encouraging and promoting WSHG in a large scale in the country. Beside this Reserve Bank of India (RBI) also take decision regarding allow to saving accounts in their bank for accessing banking services, facilities. This was a great revolution to the WSHGs movement for the rural people who are deprived from such facilities. WSHGs have that capability which helps to combine the rural development and transforms them into desired output such as social, economic, political and technological value (Microfinance and Rural Development, 2009).

In Sikkim, the concept of WSHGs was introduced with the initiative taken by Sikkim Rural Development Agency (SRDA) in 1999. This scheme is centrally sponsored scheme and the financing of the programme which was shared between the Centre and State in the ratio of 75:25. But from 15th Sepetember, 2008, the Funding Pattern has been changed i.e., 90:10 vide GOI Letter No.G.20011/02/2008-SGSY-I Dated 18th November, 2008 (Annual Report, RDD,

Government of Sikkim, 2008-2009). In order to improve the socio-economic status of the village, WSHG working under the National Rural Livelihood Mission (NRLM) and North East Rural Livelihoods Project (NERLP). The objective of NRLM is to alleviation of poverty among rural Below Poverty Line (BPL) through promotion of varied and beneficial self employment opportunities (Annual Report, 2013-14). WSHG is one of the institutions which is Universal mobilization of BPL households into effective self-managed and self-governed (ibid). NERLP is a World Bank funded project which is to implemented in the states for the alleviation of poverty. The objective of NERLP is to improve rural livelihoods, mainly focused to the women, unemployed youth, and the most disadvantaged section of people in the North Eastern States. They provide economic opportunities, adoption of agricultural sustainability and natural resources management (ibid). At Present, Sikkim State Rural Livelihood Mission (SSRLM) is implemented all six districts. It is observing in-depth process in gradual manner (Annual Report, 2019-20).

In Sikkim, SSRLM under Rural Development Department has been functioning in all the districts of Sikkim. The main purpose of the project is to ameliorate the quality of life of the rural poor families with the help of sustainability of capacity building and motivation of WSHG members. Now, there are more than 5,200 WSHG with 50,000 members in the state. The WSHG are join together into approximately 500 federations at Ward Level, Gram Panchayat Level and Block Level. SSRLM is also helping and promoting 211 producers Groups and 7 Producer Organization operating across the state. They are occupied in various farm and non-farm activities (SRLM Report, 2022).

Chumbong-Chakung is the blocks in the Soreng district of West Sikkim have taken sample study. The study was conducted at Chakung village under Chumbong-Chakung block of Soreng district of West Sikkim. In the village, found that most of the WSHGs have less than nine members group. There is no any age bar to become members in the group. Every member of WSHGs collect Rs.50 to Rs.200 per members for average monthly saving of group. The inter-group loaning practice among the groups which is less costly rates of interest ranging Rs.1 per month for WSHG members and Rs. 5 per month for nonmembers. But earlier, there was a 2/100 per month for WSHG members. The majority of the WSHGs have engaged in activities such as ginger cultivation, poultry activities, piggyery, milching cows, vegetable cultivation, pickle making, tailoring, toy making, knitting, mask making, mushroom cultivation but have faced the marketing

problems for their product. But in Sikkim, the WSHG members takes loan from WSHG fund predominantly for their medical treatment, marriage ceremony, children's education and festival of people (MART Report,2011). There are many financial institutions and bank branches which provide financial support and encourage to WSHGs. SRDA and RDD had organized annual fair and exhibitions in the market where selected WSHGs from various districts of Sikkim showcase of their individual group's products (Mukhia, 2016).

2. Review of Related Literature

Anand, Saxena, Martinez, & Dang (2020) have discussed on their article "Can Women's Self-help Groups Contribute to Sustainable Development? Evidence of capability Changes from Northern India" about the SHG members. The findings resulted that the SHG have more potentiality index in several life realms than non-SHG members. SHGs have reduced the poverty and women empowerment which indicates the potentialities of women in various places being self-employed, improvement in standard of living of people and importance of life. It enhanced the social environment so as to bring the development of culture and custom in the society. The study revealed that SHGs have potentialities to work on low or middle income level, gender equality and quality of life. Further, SHGs laid down emphasis towards the micro-finance program, training, health, education and socio-political encouragement.

Badruddin (2017) has analysed the self-help groups. In his study, it was found that the participation of women in SHGs made an important role on their empowerment both in social and economic aspects. This study showed the addresses the self-help groups. He observed that the self-help group is a participatory endeavour of women, which they are trying to secure through three adjectives of power, such as social, political and psychological-that would empower them and improve their lives.

Das (2016) in his paper titled Role of SHGs in Socioeconomic Change of Rural Women': A Micro Level Study has revealed that the social status and empowerment of respondents' women were increased after joining SHGs. It has also empowered women members largely to increase self-confidence and positive behavioural changes in the post-SHG period. It also showed that there was a significant increase in the amount of saving after joining SHG. The researcher suggested that the SHG members feel free to work with their groups. It leads them to participate on various social welfare activities with good co-operation. The SHG can play vital role to creating a difference in economic conditions, social status, decision making and by increasing women participants in other activities.

Selvakumar & Samundeeswari (2015) in their study has emphasized the participation of women in Self Help Groups (SHGs) made a significant impact on their empowerment both in social and economic aspects. This study revealed women empowerment through self-help groups in Krishnagiri district of Tamilnadu. The result of the study found that the SHGs have more impact on economic and social conditions. Further, the study showed that after joining SHG is not just for the credit as it led to an empowerment process both economically and socially.

Dhakar and Nepal (2016) have mentioned that they attempted in their study, micro-finance is the services that provide savings, credit services to the rural poor in the community and focussed on uplifting the socio-economic status of women in Nepal. Result revealed that focussed on finding out the contribution of microfinance on socio-economic development of rural community, alleviate the burden of loan for farmers, various social development works, microfinance and to lessen the poverty. It also showed that majority of the respondents 86.9% reported that their living standard had improved. However, their findings suggested that there was a need to standardised internal management system of microfinance which provide the service more efficiently and effectively.

3. Rationale of the study

Women plays indispensable role in the society which helps to contribute more to the country. But they are deprived from providing the contribution as they are rural backwardness and other social complications in the society. The study mainly concentrates on socio-economic development through WSHG. The study has been conducted in the sample area with special interest to find out the role and significance of WSHG towards socio-economic development in the area. So, the research work is based on WSHGs: A change agent for socio-economic development and economic position of women, the way in which they are empowered and to identify the challenges they encountered.

4. Research Questions

1. What is the socio-economic status of WSHGs ?
2. What is the problem faced by WSHG member ?

5. Objectives of the Study

1. To study the socio-economic status of WSHGs in the study areas.
2. To identify the problems faced by the WSHGs' members.

6. Research Hypothesis

The research hypothesis are as follows: -

- H₁: There is significant change in the economic status after joining WSHGs.

7. Methodology

The study was conducted at Chakung village under Chumbong-Chakung block of Soreng District of West Sikkim. The sample size is considered for the study is 20 WSHGs consisting 112 respondents from selected village. In this present study, 20 WSHGs were selected on random basis taking 6 members from each group in which total 120 members as a respondent but 8 respondents have not responded questionnaire. A simple random sampling technique was used. The questionnaire was prepared for both WSHGs leaders and members for different villages and interview schedules has prepared.

The study is exploratory in nature and both primary and secondary data has been used in the present study. The primary data for this study is collected from 1st December, 2022 to 31st January, 2023. The primary data has been accessed from the WSHG with the help of questionnaire prepared. The secondary data regarding WSHG and microfinance has been accessed from books, internet, journals, articles, periodicals, newspaper and other sources etc.

The descriptive and inferential statistics has been used for analyzing the data. The descriptive statistics tool such as simple percentage, mean, average, and standard deviation were used. In this study, frequency table's chart was also used. In order to testing the hypotheses, chi-square test and descriptive statistics were used.

8. Result and Discussion

Keeping in view the objectives of the study an attempt is made to analysis of results of collected data has been carried. To begin with the socio-economic status of women WSHG members, total household income of WSHGs, total household expenditure of WSHGs and total saving of WSHGs.

Table 1: Social Status of WSHGs

Variable	No. of respondents	Percentage
Age		
21-30	26	23.21
31-40	30	26.78
41-50	31	27.70
51-60	14	12.5
61-70	8	7.14
71-80	2	1.79
81-90	1	0.89

Marital Status		
Married	94	83.93
Unmarried	13	11.61
Widow	4	3.57
Separated	1	0.89
Education		
Illiterate	18	16.07
Primary (I-V)	27	24.11
Junior High School (VI-VIII)	29	25.89
Secondary School (IX-X)	19	16.96
Senior Secondary (XI-XII)	10	8.93
Graduate	7	6.25
Post Graduate	2	1.79
Occupation		
Farmers and Agriculture labour	80	71.43
Business	5	4.46
Housewife	11	9.82
Wage labour	10	8.93
Tailoring/Handlooms	6	5.36
Religion		
Hindu	23	20.54
Buddhists	42	37.50
Christian	47	41.96
Category		
OBC (Central list)	81	72.32
OBC (State List)	1	0.89
Schedule Tribe (ST)	27	24.11
Schedule Caste (SC)	3	2.68
Type of Family		
Joint	39	34.82
Nuclear	73	65.18
No. of Family members		
1-3	36	32.14
4-6	68	60.72
7-9	8	7.14
Nature of house		
Pucca (Cemented Buildings)	90	80.35
Semi pucca (Wooden House)	15	13.39
Kaccha (Hut, thatched)	7	6.26

Source: Computed by Author using primary data through field survey

Age Structure

The age is one of the important components of socioeconomic status of WSHGs. It assists to make right decision in the groups, so as to strengthen the performance of the groups. In the table shows 4 that 23.21 per cent of respondents fall in the age groups of 21-30 years, 26.78 per cent in 31-40, 27.70 per cent in 41-50 years, 12.5 per cent in 51-60, 7.14 per cent in 61-70 years, 1.79 per cent in 71-80 years and 0.89 per cent in 81-90 years. It is found that the most of the WSHGs in the village lies between 21-30, 31-40 and 41-50 years, which specify that the age group is actively participating in the WSHGs for their improvement of living standard and for their livelihood.

Marital Status

Marriage in our society is highly cherished (Ekong, 2003). It is shows that the 83.93 per cent of WSHGs are married, 11.61 per cent are unmarried, very few groups are widow and separated. This indicate that the married women are energetically participate in the WSHGs activities as comparison with unmarried, widow and separated.

Education Status

Education is one of the important tools which helps to provide the chance for gaining knowledge and skills that will facilitate people to grow their capability and become successful members of society. When the increase in the educational standards of the respondent may create full potential for rural development. This will help to improve better performance of WSHGs and

gaining the level of income of members. In this study, it is shows that the majority of the respondents i.e. 25.89 per cent and 24.11 per cent belong to the primary (I-V) and junior high school level of education (VI-VIII), similarly followed by secondary school level (IX-X) are 16.96 per cent, senior secondary level (XI-XII) are 8.93 per cent, Graduate level are 6.25 per cent, Post Graduate are 1.79 per cent and 16.07 per cent are still illiterate. It is found that the majority of the WSHGs have attained the primary and junior high school in the villages. Therefore, it is one of the important decision and courage of women empowerment through the education.

Occupation

Occupation is the tools which helps to compute or estimate living standard of people. Table 1 shows that the most of the respondents are engaged in the farmers and agriculture labour i.e., 71.43 per cent, similarly followed by housewife (9.82 per cent), wage labour (8.93 per cent), Tailoring/handloom (5.36), and in business (4.46 per cent). In the present study clearly mention that the majority of respondent are engaged in farmer and agriculture labour. Overall, the study revealed the main occupation of the respondents are agriculture in the sample village.

Religion

In this study, the tables resulted that, majority of respondents belongs to Christian religion is 41.96 per cent, Buddhist is 37.50 percent and Hindu is 20.54 per cent in the village.

Social Category

In this study, the table 1 show that the WSHGs from four social categories only. The four social

categories are Other Backward Central (Central List), Other Backward Central (State List), Scheduled Tribe (ST), Scheduled Caste (SC). It is revealed that out of 112 respondents, 72.32 per cent of WSHGs are from OBC (ST), 24.11 per cent are from ST, 2.68 per cent are from SC, only 0.89 per cent are from OBC (SL). Overall, it is pointed that OBC (SL) community are considered to be very less in the village.

Type of family

From the study, it is indicating that majority of the respondents i.e. 65.18 per cent are from nuclear family and 34.82 per cent from joint family. It revealed that the women from the nuclear family have greater privilege and power for taking part and contribution in the WSHGs.

Number of family members

Family size is one of the socio-economic factors which measure the status of people in the society. In this study, indicates that the most of the respondents of the WSHGs are 60.72 per cent having household size of 4-6 members per household, 32.14 per cent respondents whose household size having 1-3 members per household and 7.14 per cent of respondents are from 7-9 members per household. Larger size family members are less participation in the groups because of lack of counselling and motivation of rural people.

Nature of house

House is an important component of peoples' living and life. From the study, it indicates that about 80.35 per cent of respondents have pucca house, 13.39 per cent have semi pucca house, and 6.26 per cent have kaccha house.

Table 2: Caste Structure of Respondents

Variable	No. of respondents	Percentage
Caste		
Bhutia	3	2.68
Lepcha	17	15.18
Tamang	5	4.46
Limboo	3	2.68
Rai	22	19.64
Gurung	30	26.79
Manger	21	18.75
Mukhia	6	5.35
Chettri	2	1.79
Darnal (Damai)	3	2.68

Source: Computed by Author using primary data through field survey

Caste

Caste is one of the important socioeconomic factors of the WSHGs. In this study, it was revealed that 26.79 per cent are Gurung, 19.64 per cent are Rai, 18.75 per cent are Manger, 15.18 per cent are Lepcha represent the majority of WSHGs in the sample village of West Sikkim and then accompany by Mukhia (5.35 per cent), Tamang (4.46 per cent), Bhutia (2.68 per cent), Darnal (2.68 per cent), Limboo (2.68 per cent) and Chettri (1.79 per cent). It indicates that the WSHGs are found to be strengthen in participation in the groups, decision making process and to accomplish the target objectives.

Table 3: Economic Status of WSHGs

Variable	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Income of Household (in Rs.)		
Less than 10,000	6	5.36
10,000 – 30,000	72	64.29
30,000 – 50,000	25	22.32
50,000 – 100,000	8	7.14
1,00,000 and above	1	0.89
Expenditure ((in Rs.)		
Less than 10,000	73	65.17
10,000 – 30,000	34	30.36
30,000 – 50,000	3	2.68
50,000 – 100,000	2	1.79
1,00,000 and above	0	0.00
Saving (in Rs.)		
Less than 10,000	87	77.68
10,000 -30,000	21	18.75
30,000-50,000	3	2.68
50,000-100,000	1	0.89
1,00,000 and above	0	0.00

Source: Computed by Author using primary data through field survey

Income of household

Table 3 indicates that Rs. 10000 to 30000 incomes of the family respondents are high i.e., 64.29 percent, followed by Rs. 30000 to 50000 income groups are 22.32 per cent which means that respondents of group have improve the economic conditions of households in the village. Similarly, Rs.50000 to 100000 income group are 7.14 per cent, less than 10,000 income group are 5.36 per cent and Rs. 100000 and above income group are 0.89 per cent only. Overall, in the village more than 64 per cent of the WSHGs have reported the growth and development in their economic conditions in the village.

Expenditure

Table 3 shows that the majority of WSHG (65.17 percent and 30.36 per cent) fall in the expenditure groups of less than 10000 and Rs. 10000 to 30000 per month respectively. Similarly, follow by other WSHGs (2.68 per cent & 1.79 per cent) fall in the expenditure groups Rs.30000 to 50000 and Rs. 50000 to 100000 per month respectively. In our

present study, it is revealed that expenditure of the respondents has been decrease after joining WSHGs due to the training and counselling of groups.

Saving -Table 3 shows that the most of the WSHGs have increased (77.68 per cent and 18.75 per cent) which is fall in the less than 10000 and Rs.10000 to 30000. Similarly, saving of the respondents (2.68 per cent & 0.68 per cent) fall in the Rs.30000 to 50000 and 50000 to 100000. In our sample study, it is observed that saving has been increased. The respondents of WSHGs are aware and conscious about money, how to utilize the resource and financial management process. Therefore, saving is the platform for money generation and determinants of socio economic in the area.

Hypothesis

H₀: There is no significant change in the economic conditions of rural women after joining WSHGs.

H₁: There is a significant change in the economic conditions of rural women after joining WSHGs.

Chi-Square Test (χ^2) for change in economic conditions after joining WSHGs.

The formula is, $\chi^2 = \frac{\sum (O_i - E_i)^2}{E_i}$

Table 4: There is a change in economic condition after joining WSHGs

Sl.no	Alternatives/options	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)	χ^2
1.	Very Convenient	59	52.68	14.067
2.	Construction of House	4	3.57	
3.	Investment in land	1	0.89	
4.	Initiate business	20	17.86	
5.	Educate Children	9	8.04	
6.	Gained leadership	6	5.36	
7.	Learnt bookkeeping & accounting	8	7.14	
8.	Easy access to microcredit	5	4.46	
	Total	112	100	

Source: Computed by Author using primary data through field survey

Expected Value (E_i) = $\frac{112}{8} = 14$, Calculated value = 181.12, Table Value = 14.067, Degree of freedom = (n-1), = (8-1) = 7, Alpha value = 0.05

According to the hypothesis, the expected value is obtained 14, the calculated value is 181.12 more

than the critical value of (χ^2) is 14.067 at 5 percent level of significance (α), therefore, null hypothesis is rejected here. Hence, it is concluding that there is a significant change in an economic position after the joining the WSHGs. It is clear from the above results; we can say that the economic benefit has increased after joining WSHGs in the study area.

Figure 1: There is a change in an economic position after joining WSHGs

Problem faced by the WSHGs

In the present study, there are various problems regarding WSHGs in the sample area in which they are facing problems such as lack of marketing facilities, lack of adequate training facilities, lack of financial support from financial institutions and family members, inadequate socio-economic problems, lack of new technology and knowledge, lack of leadership qualities as they should be insightful and expertness in the area, very low demand of WSHG product even though good quality of product produce, very low price for product due to the lack of awareness of product produce by group in the rural area, very less credit facilities available and found absence of collaborative attitude towards WSHGs members from financial institution.

Major Findings of the study

From the above analysis the following findings are as follows: -

1. The demographic and social-economic status of the respondents have indicated positive sign and favourable for the rural development in the study area. Therefore, there is change in socio-economic conditions after joining the WSHGs.
2. The average monthly household income and saving of respondents has increased after joining the WSHGs in the West Sikkim.

3. WSHG members were participated and engaged or initiate small business in their locality which enhances the living standard of members and self-reliant.

4. In the present study, it is shows that active involvement and participation in the WSHGs, there is an absolutely development in social, economic and physiological spheres in the district.

5. The various problems faced by the WSHGs in the area/locality that it is necessary to reduce the problems with the help of improving socio-economic and financial assistance. This will help to accomplish key driver of sustainable rural development in the sample area.

Suggestions and policy implications

Taking into consideration, the socio-economic status and rural development of WSHG in the sample area, the following suggestion are constructed:

1. The Government and NGOs should organize the orientation, workshop, and motivational classes to the WSHGs in rural area so as to achieve the knowledge and awareness of groups, importance of microfinance and educate women which lead for development of leadership qualities.
2. It is advised to the Government should provide the vocational training opportunities to all WSHG members compulsorily, so that they become self-sufficient, self-reliant and empower themselves for rural development.

3. The Government and NGOs should take necessary step for the marketing facilities of product manufacture by the WSHGs in the rural area.

4. It is suggested that Government should concentrate towards problem faced by WSHG in the village, in order to prevent loss from their business in the locality which means not to harm their livelihood in the area.

Conclusion

In Sikkim, WSHGs is one of the burning issues which helps to develop women in the rural area. It made a very remarkable achievement has been made over the last five years in the context of WSHG as self-reliant and self-sufficient. The socio-economic status has been improved or strengthen in the sample area. WSHGs become empowerment of women, engagement in small business activities, increase in the level of income, mode of bank saving, decrease the expenditure level and change in their life style. After joining the WSHG, there is a huge change in their standard of living and women empowerment. It is becoming an economic undependable or independence situation in regard the microfinance to awake at all aspect. The study revealed that brings the stability in their personal income through WSHG. Through the WSHG activities, the respondents have upgraded the confidence, decision making, capacity of the women and leadership qualities. WSHG has become one of the effective tools for social, economic and unemployment problem in the rural area and this helps to control the unemployment issues through the small economic activities. The orientation of WSHG is mainly for economic and social empowerment. It helps to link and bridging the gap between the financial institution and the rural poor people. WSHG helps to reduce poverty, encourage women empowerment and rural development. The Government alone is not possible for women empowerment, so that collective efforts of all the members of the groups must play respective roles for achieving their goals.

References

1. Anand, P., Saxena, S., Martinez, R. G., & Dang, H.-A. H. (2020). Can Women's Self-help Groups Contribute to Sustainable Development? Evidence of Capability Changes from Northern India. *Journal of Human Development and Capabilities*, 21(2), 137–160.
2. Annual Report, 2008-09, Rural Development Department, Government of Sikkim.
3. Annual Report, 2013-14, Rural Development Department, Government of Sikkim.
4. Annual Report, 2019-20, Rural Development Department, Government of Sikkim.
5. Badruddin, S. T. (2017). *Self Help Groups : An Emerging Power in Women empowerment*. Asian Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies , 5 (10), 80-82.
6. Das, J. (2016, February). Role of Self Help Groups in Socioeconomic Change of Rural Women: a Micro Level Study. *Indian Streams Research Journal (International Recognized Multidisciplinary Research Journal)*, 6(1), 1-11.
7. Dhakal, C. P., and Nepal, G. (2016). Contribution of Micro-Finance on Socio-Economic Development of Rural Community. *Journal of Advanced Academic Research (JAAR)* , 3 (I), 134-141.
8. Ekong, E.E. (2003). *An introduction to rural sociology (2nded.)*. Uyo, Nigeria: Dove Educational Publisher Ltd.
9. Fakoya, E.O.(2000). *Farmers use of sustainable land management practices in Ondo State, Nigeria (Doctoral Dissertation)*. Department of Agricultural Extension and Rural Development, University of Ibadan, 160
- a. Gadkari, R. K. (2015). *Role of Microfinance in Entrepreneurial Development*.
10. Gaikwad, M., & Reddy, S. (2013). *The Impact of SHGs on Women Development: A Study of Kummanpally Village, Andhra Pradesh (India)*. *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science (IOSR-JHSS)*, 7(1), 42-48.
11. Gautam, G., & Chettri, R. (2016, June). *Socio-Economic Implications of Self Help Groups and Women Empowerment in Geyzing Subdivision of West District of Sikkim*. *International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research in Science Society and Culture(IJIRSSC)*, 2(1), 289-310.
12. MART. (2011). *'Livelihood based Agri Business and Market Studies for North East Rural Livelihood Project'*, Final Report, Sikkim. Noida MART
13. Mukhia, S. (2016). *Women's Empoernment Through Self Help Group in Sikkim : A Sociological Study*.
14. PIP. (2011) *North East Rural Livelihoods Project (NERLP) Ministry of DoNER, Govt. of India*
15. Selvakumar, D. S., & Samundeeswari, B. (2015). *Impact of Self Help Groups on Empowerment of Women: A study in Krishnagiri District, Tamilnadu*. *Asian Journal of Business and Management*, 3(1), 54-57.
16. Sharma, G. (2014). *Microfinance through SHGs and the Empowerment of Women: A case study of some selected SHGs of Sikkim*. *Asian Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies* , 2 (7), 271-279.
17. *Sikkim State Report, 2010*
18. *Sikkim State Rural Livelihood Misson, 2016-2022*
19. Siwach, M., and Singh, B. (2018, March). *Role of NABARD: An analysis of SHG: Bank*

- linkage programme in Haryana: An overview. *International Journal of Academic Research and Development*, 3(2). 355-358.
20. Status of Microfinance in India 2021-22, NABARD.
 21. Sussan, M. U., and Obamuyi, T. (2018). The Impact of Microfinance Bank on Entrepreneurship Development in Nigeria. *Journal of Business and Economic Development* , 3(2), 51-61.
 22. V, M. (2016, September). A study on self-help group bank linkage programme in India. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Development* , 3(9), 23-26 .
 23. <http://www.sa-dhan.net>
 24. <https://www.moneycontrol.com/news/business/banks/microfinance-industry-logs-13-growth-in-last-quarter-shows-sa-dhan-data-8525371.html>
 25. <https://sikkim.gov.in/DepartmentsMenu/cooperationdepartment/Apex%20Cooperatives/sisco>
 26. <http://www.onefivenine.com/india/villages/West-District/Soreng/Chakung>
 27. <https://www.census2011.co.in/data/village/261097-chakung-sikkim.html#:~:text=Average%20Sex%20Ratio%20of%20Chakung,than%20Sikkim%20average%20of%20957>.